

A Bayesian Approach to Spatio-Temporal Extreme Rainfall Modeling: Insights from West Java

Achi Rinaldi ^{a,*}, Anik Djuraidah ^b, Aji Hamim Wigena ^b

^a Department of Mathematics Education, UIN Raden Intan Lampung, Indonesia

^b Department of Statistics, Bogor Agricultural University, Indonesia

Corresponding author: *achi@radenintan.ac.id

Abstract—The increasing phenomenon of extreme rainfall due to global climate change poses a serious challenge to hydrometeorological disaster risk management. Spatio-temporal modeling has proven to be a practical approach to understanding the distribution and intensity of extreme rainfall; however, its implementation still faces methodological obstacles, primarily due to the complexity of spatial and temporal data structures and limitations in the flexibility of grid-based spatial zoning. This study proposes the development of a Bayesian-based spatio-temporal model specifically designed to estimate extreme rainfall in West Java Province, a region with complex topographical conditions and high vulnerability to disasters. Three types of models were built, namely linear models with time trends, additive models without interaction, and additive models with spatial-temporal interaction. Spatial effects were modeled through the Conditional Autoregressive (CAR) approach, while parameter estimation was performed using the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) method. Evaluation results using RMSEP and DIC metrics show that the additive model with spatial-temporal interaction has the most optimal performance in predicting extreme rainfall. Longitude and latitude factors are identified as the dominant determining variables, which reinforces the critical role of geographical aspects in spatial estimation. This research not only expands the application scope of Bayesian methods in climate modeling but also provides a strong scientific basis for the development of early warning systems and data-driven disaster mitigation strategies. This approach can potentially be adapted for use in other regions and combined with Internet of Things (IoT) technologies to produce more precise and adaptive real-time extreme rainfall predictions.

Keywords— Bayesian; CAR; extreme rainfall; Spatio-temporal.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Extreme rainfall can cause significant impacts, such as floods and landslides, which affect multiple sectors [1], [2], including infrastructure, agriculture, and people's livelihoods [3]. This issue becomes critical to study and analyze, given the high risk posed [4]. In Indonesia, the West Java region stands out due to its high population density [5], unique geographical characteristics, and vulnerability to extreme weather events [6]. With a population of more than 50 million, West Java is the most populous province in Indonesia [7], where extreme rainfall events can have widespread impacts on urban and rural areas and economic activity [8]. Additionally, West Java hosts major watersheds such as the Citarum and Ciliwung rivers, which play a vital role in water resource management but are highly sensitive to extreme rainfall patterns [9]. The region's topography, consisting of mountains and lowlands, makes it prone to landslides and

flooding. Therefore, accurate rainfall estimation is crucial to support disaster risk mitigation efforts and evidence-based policy planning [10], [11] particularly in vulnerable areas like West Java.

Extreme rainfall modeling has incorporated various components designed to enhance accuracy, including spatial and temporal elements [11]. Spatial modeling is often employed to map disaster-prone areas, such as the creation of extreme rainfall zones in West Java [12], or rainfall prediction maps in Switzerland using the return value approach [13]. Similar research has been conducted by [14], [15], who utilized the CAR (Conditional Auto-Regressive) model to capture spatial and temporal patterns of extreme rainfall. Spatio-temporal models based on CAR have been developed using various approaches. Bernardinelli et al. [16] separated spatio-temporal random components, assuming a linear time trend. Ismail et. al [17] described spatio-temporal variability in three forms: spatial effects over the entire period, temporal

effects for each spatial unit, and space-time interactions. Napier et al. [18] divided random effects into two components: a time component and a spatial component with differing spatial variations for each period. Previous studies by [19], [20] applied a multivariate approach with a first-order auto-regressive method and spatial correlation matrix to model spatio-temporal structures. However, all the above studies still use response data that is assumed to follow the family exponential distribution; no one has used modelling for data with extreme distributions.

Hierarchical Bayes is a method widely used by researchers to estimate parameters in spatio-temporal models [21], [22]. One of the advantages of this method is that the distribution assumptions tend to be more flexible and are supported by programming packages available in various software such as the R program. Previous research on spatio-temporal extreme rainfall discusses local, regional, and teleconnections scale synchronization patterns between various locations in CONUS [23], then discusses spatio-temporal extreme rainfall in West Java using a simple statistical approach [24], while the research conducted by Bambang et. al. [25] does not use GEV distribution to identify extreme intensity.

However, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no studies have specifically discussed the development of a spatio-temporal Bayesian model to estimate extreme rainfall patterns in West Java, considering the region's specific geographical and local climate conditions. Therefore, this study employs the Hierarchical Bayes method to estimate parameters, while the method used to identify extreme rainfall is the Block Maxima approach with the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution. Spatial effects are modeled through specific extreme rainfall zones previously studied in [26], while temporal effects are modelled based on annual time [27]. By integrating the GEV and INLA distributions, this study provides a more efficient and robust framework for predicting extreme rainfall. The findings from this research are expected to support disaster risk mitigation efforts and serve as a basis for formulating more practical policies. Moreover, this approach opens opportunities for further studies to apply similar methods to other extreme phenomena and across diverse geographical regions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

A. Integrated Laplace Approximation

The most commonly used method for obtaining posterior distribution in Bayes modeling is Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) [28]. This is due to efficiency and accuracy, also due to the rapid development of computing. The rapid development of technology raises numerical methods that can be solved computationally, such as Variational Bayes (VB). This method has been developed by several researchers, such as Boškoski, et. al. [29], after review, it turns out that VB has a weakness which is the estimation of posterior variance tends to be underestimated.

Another approach to get posterior distribution other than MCMC and VB is Expectation-Propagation (EP). The principles of the EP approach are similar to VB, and both methods are designed to produce faster estimates of the MCMC method. But in its development, it was found that EP had an over-estimated posterior variance [30].

Some methods for producing posterior distribution are already known advantages and disadvantages. Martin et. al. have developed a method to produce better and more efficient estimates than the methods described previously [31]. This method is called Integrated Laplace Approximation (INLA) [32]. As the name implies, this method uses the Laplace approach.

Suppose that $f(x)$ is known as the probability density function (p.d.f.) of the random variable X , then $\int f(x)dx$ can be calculated via $\int \exp(\log(fx)) dx$. Calculation of $\log(fx)$ can be solved by Taylor series expansion, which evaluates $x = x_0$, which can be described as:

$$\log(fx) \approx \log f(x_0) + (x - x_0) \left. \frac{\partial \log f(x)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0} + \frac{(x - x_0)^2}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x_0}$$

If x_0 is assumed to be equal to $x^* = \arg \max_x \log(fx)$, then $\left. \frac{\partial \log f(x)}{\partial x} \right|_{x=x_0} = 0$, so that the Taylor series expansion becomes:

$$\log(fx) \approx \log f(x^*) + \frac{(x - x^*)^2}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x^*}$$

$\int f(x)dx$ can be described as:

$$\begin{aligned} \int f(x)dx &= \int \exp(\log f(x^*)) dx \\ &\approx \int \exp \left(\log f(x^*) + \frac{(x - x^*)^2}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x^*} \right) dx \\ &= \exp(\log f(x^*)) \int \exp \left(\frac{(x - x^*)^2}{2} \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x^*} \right) dx, \end{aligned}$$

suppose that $\sigma^{2*} = -1 / \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x^*}$, then the equation can

be approached into Normal distribution: $\int f(x)dx \approx \int \exp(\log f(x^*)) \int \exp \left(-\frac{(x - x^*)^2}{2\sigma^{2*}} \right)$, which mean is x^* and variance is σ^{2*} . If the integral is determined by the interval (α, β) , then the Laplace approach becomes: $\int_{\alpha}^{\beta} f(x)dx \approx f(x^*)\sqrt{2\pi\sigma^{2*}}(\Phi(\beta) - \Phi(\alpha))$, with $\Phi(\cdot)$ as a Normal cumulative distribution function (x^*, σ^{2*}) . For an example $f(x)$ is pdf of Gamma distribution which known as: $\exp(-bx)x^{a-1}$, and $x, a, b > 0$, then the Laplace approach starts with counting [33]:

$$\begin{aligned} \log f(x) &= (a - 1)\log x - bx + C \\ \frac{\partial \log f(x)}{\partial x} &= \frac{a - 1}{x} - b \\ \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} &= -\frac{a - 1}{x^2}, \text{ if } \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} = 0 \text{ then } x^* \\ &= \frac{a - 1}{b} \text{ for } a > 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\sigma^{2*} = -1 / \left. \frac{\partial^2 \log f(x)}{\partial x^2} \right|_{x=x^*} = \frac{a-1}{b^2}, \text{ Gamma distribution can}$$

be approached by: $\text{Gamma}(a, b) \approx \text{Normal}(x^* = \frac{a-1}{b}, \sigma^{2*} = \frac{a-1}{b^2})$.

The main purpose of Bayes' estimation is to find the posterior distribution of each parameter that can be described as:

$$p(\theta_i|\mathbf{y}) = \int p(\theta_i, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})d\boldsymbol{\psi} = \int p(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})p(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})d\boldsymbol{\psi} \quad (1)$$

and each element of the hyperparameter is:

$$p(\psi_k|\mathbf{y}) = \int p(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})d\psi_{-k} \quad (2)$$

Laplace approximation steps to get posterior distribution are as follows:

1) Calculate $p(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})$ through marginal distribution $p(\psi_k|\mathbf{y})$:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y}) = \frac{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})}{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} = \frac{p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi})}{p(\mathbf{y})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} = \frac{p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\psi})}{p(\mathbf{y})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \propto \frac{p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\psi})}{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \approx \frac{p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi})p(\boldsymbol{\psi})}{\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}=\boldsymbol{\theta}^*(\boldsymbol{\psi})} = \tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y}), \quad (3)$$

2) Calculate $p(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})$ to get $p(\theta_i|\mathbf{y})$:

Suppose $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is a parameter vector that can be written as $\boldsymbol{\theta} = (\theta_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i})$, through the Laplace approach can be described:

$$p(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{p((\theta_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i})|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})}{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} = \frac{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})}{p(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})p(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \propto \frac{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})}{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \approx \frac{p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})}{\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})} \Big|_{\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}=\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}^*(\boldsymbol{\psi})} = \tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y}), \quad (4)$$

$\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})$ is a Laplace estimator of $p(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{-i}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})$

After getting $\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})$ through equation (4) and $\tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})$ through equation (6), then the posterior of $p(\theta_i|\mathbf{y})$ can be estimated by:

$$\tilde{p}(\theta_i|\mathbf{y}) \approx \int \tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}, \mathbf{y})\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})d\boldsymbol{\psi}, \quad (5)$$

The integral form of equation (7) can be solved by numerical methods through:

$$\tilde{p}(\theta_i|\mathbf{y}) \approx \sum_j \tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}, \mathbf{y})\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}|\mathbf{y})\Delta_j \quad (6)$$

The posterior distribution estimation is solved by the INLA algorithm, the stages are:

1. Explores the hyperparameter posterior distribution $\tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})$ from equation (4) to get $\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}$ for the numerical integration required in Equation (8). Locate the value of $\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}$ by optimizing $\log \tilde{p}(\boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y})$ with respect to $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ through the Newton-Raphson method.
2. Compute the negative Hessian \mathbf{H} .
3. Suppose $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$ is covariance of $\boldsymbol{\psi}$, with $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \mathbf{H}^{-1}$. Compute the eigen decomposition $\boldsymbol{\Sigma} = \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{1/2}\mathbf{V}^t$.

4. Determine \mathbf{z} with formula:

$$\boldsymbol{\psi}(\mathbf{z}) = \boldsymbol{\psi}^* + \mathbf{V}\boldsymbol{\Lambda}^{1/2}\mathbf{z}.$$

5. Posterior $\tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}, \mathbf{y})$ is evaluated for each $\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}$, then the value of $\tilde{p}(\theta_i|\boldsymbol{\psi}^{(j)}, \mathbf{y})$ is calculated using equation (8).

B. Spatio-Temporal Model for Extreme Value

The development of the spatio-temporal model has been carried out in the fields of health, economics, and climatology. There are several models used in this study, namely:

1) Spatio-temporal Model with Linear Trend:

Bernardinelli et al. [16] describe spatio-temporal random components with linear trends in time separately. This model is very suitable for estimating areas which have a downward trend or increasing trend in time. This model can be written as:

$$y_{it} \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_{it}); \quad \lambda_{it} = E_{it}\rho_{it}; \\ \log \rho_{it} = \eta_{it} \\ \boldsymbol{\eta}_{it} = \mathbf{X}'_{it}\boldsymbol{\beta} + \mathbf{v}_i + \mathbf{v}_t + (\boldsymbol{\alpha} + \boldsymbol{\delta}_i) \times t, \quad (9)$$

y_{it} is the variable response in the i -location, t -time, and \mathbf{X}_{it} are explanatory variables, $i = 1, 2, \dots, K$ shows the number of spatial units, $t = 1, 2, \dots, N$ is the time period, $\boldsymbol{\beta}$ is the coefficient of the explanatory variable, η_{it} is a link function, \mathbf{v}_i is a spatial unstructured residual component assuming $v_i \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_v^2)$, while \mathbf{v}_t is a spatial structured random component modeled by Conditional Auto-regressive / CAR [34].

$$v_i|v_{-i} \sim \text{Normal}(\mu_i + \sum_{j=1}^n r_{ij}(v_j - \mu_j), s_i^2), \quad (10)$$

μ_i is the average for the i -area and $s_i^2 = \frac{\sigma_v^2}{N_i}$ is the range that depends on the number of neighborhoods (N_i). The value r_{ij} shows a spatial relationship that can be calculated with $\phi \times w_{ij}$, with $|\phi| < 1$ and w_{ij} described as:

$$w_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{adjacent} \\ 0, & \text{others} \end{cases}$$

If \mathbf{W} is a matrix that contains w_{ij} and $\mathbf{S} = \text{diag}(s_1, \dots, s_n)$, then $\mathbf{v} \sim \text{Normal}(\boldsymbol{\mu}, (\mathbf{I} - \rho\mathbf{W})^{-1}\mathbf{S}^2)$.

The parameter that shows the global effect of time is α , while δ_i is the effect of a linear trend of time on the i -area which assumed $\delta_i \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_\delta^2)$, t is variable in time. So, the parameter that is estimated in this model is $\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\beta_0, \alpha, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}, \boldsymbol{\delta}\}$. If precision defines as $\tau = 1/\sigma^2$, then hyperparameter is $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \{\tau_v, \tau_v, \tau_\delta\}$.

2) Spatio-temporal Additive Model:

Knorr-Held [35] describes the random component of spatio-temporal effect into three forms, the first is the spatial effect for the entire time period, second is the temporal effect for each spatial unit, and the third is assuming for space and time interaction. The additive spatio-temporal model without interaction describes as:

$$y_{it} \sim \text{Binomial}(n_{it}\pi_{it}); \quad \eta_{it} = \log(\pi_{it}/(1 - \pi_{it})) \\ \eta_{it} = \mathbf{X}'_{it}\boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i + v_t + \gamma_t + \phi_t, \quad (11)$$

$\mathbf{X}'_{it}\boldsymbol{\beta}$, v_i , v_t are equal with the first, while γ_t is modeled as a dynamic temporal effect using first order random walk $\gamma_t|\gamma_{t-1} \sim \text{Normal}(\gamma_{t-1}, \sigma^2)$. ϕ_t is a mean residual temporal which assumed as $\phi_t \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_\phi^2)$. The same with the

first model if precision is defining as $\tau = 1/\sigma^2$, then the hyper-parameter $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \{\tau_v, \tau_v, \tau_\gamma, \tau_\phi\}$.

3) Spatio-temporal Additive Model:

The spatio-temporal additive model with interaction is a development of Knorr-Held [35] model which described as :

$$\eta_{it} = \mathbf{X}'_{it}\boldsymbol{\beta} + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}, \quad (12)$$

with $\delta_{it} \sim \text{Normal}(0, \sigma_\delta^2)$, while the other components are assumed to be the same as the previous model. Hyper-parameters for this model are $\boldsymbol{\varphi} = \{\tau_v, \tau_v, \tau_\gamma, \tau_\phi, \tau_\delta\}$.

Rushworth et al. (2014) modeled the spatio-temporal structure using the first-order multivariate auto-regressive, so that in this study the temporal structure γ_t was modeled by random walk order-1 which is $\gamma_t | \gamma_{t-1} \sim \text{Normal}(\gamma_{t-1}, \sigma^2)$ and also auto-regressive order-1.

The model in equation (9), (11), and (12) are spatio-temporal models that have been used for variables with distributed as Poisson, Binomial, and Normal distribution. This study is the development of spatio-temporal model with GEV distribution; the models used in this study can be described as follows:

Models without explanatory variable

1. The model with a linear trend.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + \nu_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t \quad (13)$$

2. The additive model.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t \quad (14)$$

3. The additive model with interaction.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it} \quad (15)$$

Models with explanatory variable

The explanatory variables are x_1 = longitude, x_2 = latitude, x_3 = monthly average rainfall, x_4 = altitude.

1. The model with a linear trend in time.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + \nu_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t \quad (16)$$

2. The additive model.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t \quad (17)$$

3. The additive model with interaction.

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}. \quad (18)$$

The spatio-temporal model built using the GEV distribution assumption because of the identification of extreme values using the Blok Maxima (BM) method. Suppose the model used is additive and interaction, then the model can be described as follows:

$$y_{it} \sim \text{GEV}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{it}, \sigma, \xi)$$

$$\eta_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + \nu_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}.$$

This model has an additive structure with the link function used is the identity function, so it can be written as $\mu_{it} = \eta_{it}$. The approach used is Gaussian Markov Random Field

(GMRF), the parameter to estimate is called latent and written as a parameter.

$\boldsymbol{\theta} = \{\boldsymbol{\beta}, v_i, \nu_i, \gamma_t, \phi_t, \delta_{it}\}$, while the hyperparameter is $\boldsymbol{\psi} = \{\sigma, \tau_v, \tau_v, \tau_\gamma, \tau_\phi, \tau_\delta\}$. Likelihood function from $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is:

$$p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}) = \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K p(y_{it}|\theta_{it}, \boldsymbol{\psi}). \quad (19)$$

All priors of the parameter $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are assumed in a normal distribution with a mean of 0 and a precision $\boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi})$, which can be written as $\boldsymbol{\theta} \sim \text{Normal}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\tau}^{-1}(\boldsymbol{\psi}))$ and probability density function (p.d.f) is:

$$p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}) = (2\pi)^{-n/2} |\boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi})|^{1/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\theta}' \boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \boldsymbol{\theta}\right) \quad (20)$$

Joint posterior from $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ and $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ is the product of the probability functions of equation (19) and prior to equation (20).

$$\begin{aligned} p(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}|\mathbf{y}) &\propto p(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}, \boldsymbol{\psi}) \\ &\propto p(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times p(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K p(y_{it}|\theta_{it}, \boldsymbol{\psi}) \\ &\propto p(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times |\boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi})|^{1/2} \\ &\times \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K \exp(\log(p(y_{it}|\theta_{it}, \boldsymbol{\psi}))) \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\propto p(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \times |\boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi})|^{1/2} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\theta}' \boldsymbol{\tau}(\boldsymbol{\psi}) \boldsymbol{\theta}\right) \\ &\quad + \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K \log(p(y_{it}|\theta_{it}, \boldsymbol{\psi})) \end{aligned}$$

GEV distribution for $\xi \neq 0$ can be written as:

$G(y) = \exp\left\{-\left(1 + \xi \frac{y-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^{-1/\xi}\right\}$, so that p.d.f. can be derived from its distribution function, which is:

$$\begin{aligned} g(y) &= \frac{d(G(y))}{dy} \\ &= \left[+\xi \left(\frac{y-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma}\right) \exp\left\{-\left[+\xi \left(\frac{y-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi}\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma} \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi-1} \exp\left\{-\left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y-\mu}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi}\right\}, \quad \text{with} \end{aligned}$$

assuming $Y_{it} \sim \text{GEV}(\mu_{it}, \sigma, \xi)$ so the likelihood function for $\xi \neq 0$ obtained from joint p.d.f. y_{it} , that is:

$$\begin{aligned} l(\mu_{it}, \sigma, \xi | y_{it}) &= \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K \left[1 \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi-1} \exp\left\{-\left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi}\right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{\sigma^{NK}} \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi-1} \exp\left\{-\left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma}\right)\right]^{-1/\xi}\right\} \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \sigma^{-NK} \prod_{t=1}^N \prod_{i=1}^K \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/(\xi+1)} \exp \left\{ - \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi} \right\} \\
\log l(\mu_{it}, \sigma, \xi | y_{it}) &= - \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K (NK \log \sigma + (1/\xi + 1) \log \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right] + \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi})
\end{aligned}$$

Through Laplace's approach, we need to find:

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \log f(y_{it} | \mu_{it}, \sigma, \xi)}{\partial y_{it}} &= - \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{(1/\xi + 1)}{\left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]} + 1/\xi \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi - 1} \\
\frac{\partial^2 \log f(y_{it} | \mu_{it}, \sigma, \xi)}{\partial y_{it}^2} &= \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{(1/\xi + 1)}{\left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^2} + (1/\xi^2 - 1) \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi - 2}
\end{aligned}$$

Joint posterior θ and ψ in equation (21) become:

$$\begin{aligned}
p(\theta, \psi | y) &= p(\psi) \times |\tau(\psi)|^{1/2} \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2} \theta' \tau(\psi) \theta \right) \\
&- \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^K NK \log \sigma + (1/\xi + 1) \log \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right] + \left[1 + \xi \left(\frac{y_{it} - \mu_{it}}{\sigma} \right) \right]^{-1/\xi} \quad (23)
\end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, the posterior distribution of $\tilde{p}(\theta_i | y)$ from equation (8) is calculated via the INLA algorithm.

C. Model Comparison

This study uses several methods to compare the fittest models, one of which is the Deviance Information Criterion (DIC). DIC calculations use simulations of posterior distribution which can be seen in Ebrahim et. al. [36], this criterion is also often solved with the logarithm of the marginal likelihood function [37]. DIC has been implemented in various software such as Bayesian Inference Using Gibbs Sampling (BUGS) and R programs. The best model criteria are to minimize DIC but maximize Marginal Log-Likelihood (MLL). DIC can be described as:

$$DIC = \widehat{D}_{avg}^{pred}(y) = 2\widehat{D}_{avg}(y) - D_{\hat{\theta}}(y)$$

with $D_{\hat{\theta}}(y) = D(y, \hat{\theta}(y))$, deviance described as: $D(y, \theta) = -2 \log p(y|\theta)$, while $2\widehat{D}_{avg}(y) = \frac{1}{L} \sum_{l=1}^L D(y, \theta^l)$.

The marginal likelihood for the M is defined as:

$$\pi(y|M) = \int \pi(y, x, \theta|M) dx d\theta$$

The tests used to fit the model are Root Mean Square Error Prediction (RMSEP) and Average Absolute Prediction Error (AAPE). RMSEP and AAPE are methods to measure the difference between the predicted value and the actual value defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
RMSEP &= \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T (y_{it} - \hat{y}_{it})^2}{S \times T}} \\
AAPE &= \frac{|\sum_{i=1}^S \sum_{t=1}^T (y_{it} - \hat{y}_{it})|}{S \times T}
\end{aligned}$$

The steps of this study are:

1. Identifying extreme rainfall data using the Block Maxima (BM) method based on 19 zones and annual blocks.
2. Modeling μ with spatio-temporal effect through an identity link function that can be described as:
 - Spatio-temporal effect with linear time trends. Without an explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_t + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$
 - i. Full model with explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + v_t + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$.
 - Additive Spatio-Temporal effect. Without an explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_t + \gamma_t + \phi_t$ Full model with explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + v_t + \gamma_t + \phi_t$.
 - Spatio-Temporal effect in Additive and Interaction form. Without explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_t + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$ Full model with explanatory variable: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_2\beta_2 + x_3\beta_3 + x_4\beta_4 + v_i + v_t + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$.
3. Determine the priorities of each parameter, with the following conditions:
 - v_i is a spatial structured random effect modeled with CAR with the distribution being $v_i | v_j \sim Normal(\mu, (\mathbf{I} - \rho \mathbf{W})^{-1} \mathbf{S}^2)$.
 - v_t is a spatial structured random effect modeled with CAR with the distribution $v_t \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$.
 - δ_i is the effect of interactions in location and time on a linear trend model, with the distribution assumed $\delta_i \sim N(0, \sigma_\delta^2)$.
 - γ_t is a temporal structured random effect modeled with 1st order random walk, while $\gamma_t | \gamma_{t-1} \sim Normal(\gamma_{t-1}, \sigma^2)$.
 - ϕ_t represents the average temporal residual with $\phi_t \sim N(0, \sigma_\phi^2)$.
 - δ_{it} is a spatio-temporal effect for additive models and interactions with $\delta_{it} \sim N(0, \sigma_\delta^2)$.
4. The hyperparameter of the model is defined as the precision that can be written as $\tau = 1/\sigma^2$. So, the hyperparameter of all models is $\varphi = \{\tau_v, \tau_v, \tau_\gamma, \tau_\phi, \tau_\delta\}$ with prior: $\log \tau_v = \log \text{Gamma}(1, 0.0001)$

$$\begin{aligned} \log \tau_v &= \log \text{Gamma}(1, 0.001) \\ \log \tau_\gamma &= \log \text{Gamma}(1, 0.0005) \\ \log \tau_\phi &= \log \text{Gamma}(1, 0.0005) \\ \log \tau_\delta &= \log \text{Gamma}(1, 0.0005) \end{aligned}$$

Prior values are determined from the default R-INLA program, as well as several alternatives that have been made in [34].

5. The hyperparameters of the GEV distribution are scale parameters (σ) and shape parameters (ξ). For ξ a value of 0.07 is determined based on the initial exploration of the estimated parameters. Precision is defined as $\tau = 1/\sigma^2$ with Gamma prior $\log(1, 0.001)$.
6. Estimating the distribution of posterior parameter models using the Integrated Laplace Approximation (INLA) method. This research uses R software version 3.4.0 and the package used is R-INLA.
7. Test the goodness of fit of the model using Deviance Information Criterion (DIC), marginal Log Likelihood, Root Mean Square Error Prediction (RMSEP), and Average Absolute Prediction Error (AAPE).

D. Data

The data used are obtained from the Meteorology Climatology and Geophysics Agency (BMKG). This data is about monthly rainfall intensity. The period of rainfall data used from 1981 to 2012. The data is taken from nineteen extreme rainfall zones in the West Java region. The area limit in the modeling is the extreme rainfall zone, as shown in Figure 1. The explanatory variables used are longitude, latitude, altitude, and average annual rainfall.

Fig. 1 Extreme rainfall zone in West Java

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Exploration

Maximum values from 19 rain zones showing rainfall for each station vary, as can be seen in Figure 2. Even though the values taken are the maximum values, it turns out that the majority of rain stations still have outliers at the top of the box diagram with lines on the long box. This shows that the distribution of data tends to extend toward the right (extreme right), which means that rainfall has a chance to far exceed its average value.

Fig. 2 Box plot monthly maximum rainfall in 19 zones (1981-2012 period)

The box plot in Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of maximum rainfall across years, which exhibits varying values. Outlier values are still clearly visible at the top of the line box plot. Outlier values indicate that rainfall based on the period of the year also has a probability to exceed its mean far. This finding is in line with the study by Meena et al.[38], who also used box plot visualization to observe the variability of annual rainfall at 62 stations in the Rajasthan region, India, over more than 50 years. They found that some years showed very high annual rainfall and deviated from the average pattern, and many stations recorded positive outliers in those years, such as 1975, 1990, 2006, and 2010. The similarity of this pattern indicates that the characteristics of extreme rainfall data in various tropical and semi-arid regions exhibit a long-tail tendency or right-tail distribution, where the maximum rainfall intensity is not only high but also occurs unevenly over time.

Fig. 3 Box plot monthly maximum rainfall in the 1981-2014 period (19 zones)

To illustrate the characteristics of maximum rainfall in the zone, a map is shown in Figure 4. Maximum rainfall shows a varied pattern both in terms of location and time factors, also seen as a cluster of several zones that indicate a spatial association.

Fig. 4 Maximum rainfall in the extreme rain zone (mm) period 1981-2012

When seen from the high intensity of rainfall over time, Figure 4 shows a pattern that is consistent with the year of the occurrence of La Nina, such as 1988, 1989, 2001, and 2010. The maximum monthly rainfall in those years is noticeably higher compared to other years. Some extreme rainfall zones, such as zones 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 show high rainfall values almost every year. This is in line with research conducted by Ardiyani et. al. [39] that certain years that have higher regression performance are selected to be recommended for use as data in posterior model development .

B. Comparison of Extreme Spatio-temporal Models

After estimating through the INLA method, models that have the best performance can be compared. In Table 1, we can see the results of the model goodness test using DIC and MLL. Small DIC and MLL values indicate an increasingly fit model.

TABLE I
DCC AND MLL

Model	DIC	MLL
Model without covariate		
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$	8456.26	-
		4921.78
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t$	8214.38	-
		4118.12
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$	8214.7	-
		4119.57

Model	DIC	MLL
Model with covariate.	DIC	MLL
$x_1 = \text{longitude}, x_2 = \text{latitude},$ $x_3 = \text{average rainfall}, x_4 =$ altitude		
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_2\beta_2 + v_i + v_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$	8283.03	-
		4195.62
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + x_2\beta_2 + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t$	8204.78	-
		4110.34
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_2\beta_2 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$	8196.00	-
		4108.36

Table 1 shows that the Spatio-temporal model with the decomposition of additive components and interactions as well as using the latitude coordinate variable is the best model because it provides the smallest DIC value. Performance prediction can be seen from the best estimation using Root Mean Square Error Prediction (RMSEP) and Absolute Average Deviance (AAPE). The smaller RMSEP and AAPE values indicate the better performance of the alleged model, Comparison of the best model estimation results in this study can also be seen in parallel with research by Rohimahastuti et al. [40], who used a spatio-temporal Bayesian approach with the INLA method and CAR structure to model the number of forest fire hotspots in Kalimantan. In line with this study, they also evaluated six different models and found that the additive model with interaction and explanatory variables produced the smallest DIC, RMSEP, and AAPE values. Although on a different topic, the similarity of the results showing that models with spatial-temporal interactions perform best provides additional validation for the model selection developed in this study.

Table 2 shows that the model with the best-predicted performance, which is an additive and interaction models using explanatory variables for longitude and average coordinates monthly rainfall. The model also has the smallest RMSEP and AAPE values.

TABLE II
RMSEP AND AAPE

Model	RMSEP	AAPE
Model without covariate		
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$	250.9943	182.3683
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t$	258.8267	185.2222
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$	259.4704	185.571
Model with covariate	RMSEP	AAPE
$x_1 = \text{longitude}, x_2 = \text{latitude},$ $x_3 = \text{average rainfall}, x_4 =$ altitude		
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_3\beta_3 + v_i + v_i + (\alpha + \delta_i) \times t$	209.7117	146.5833
Model: $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_3\beta_3 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t$	207.6539	143.7897
Model : $\mu_{it} = \beta_0 + x_1\beta_1 + x_3\beta_3 + v_i + v_i + \gamma_t + \phi_t + \delta_{it}$	200.5256	138.7312

Table 3 presents the estimated parameter values for the additive model and interactions with the latitude coordinate explanatory variables that provide the smallest DIC and marginal loglikelihood values. In general, the estimated value of the parameter gives a significant result with a marked estimation that is between the 0.025 quantile value and the

0.975 quantile value. The value of the negative latitude coefficient estimator indicates that the further south, the more likely extreme rainfall is to occur in the West Java region. This result is in line with the findings of García et al. [41], who applied a spatio-temporal hierarchical Bayesian model to analyze extreme rainfall in the Extremadura region of Spain. In their study, the location parameter (μ) of the GEV

distribution was also influenced by the spatial variable of altitude, and they found that the location parameter showed a positive spatial trend with elevation, meaning that extreme rainfall tends to be higher in areas with greater altitude. This suggests that geographical factors such as coordinates, or topography have a significant influence on the intensity of extreme rainfall in a region.

TABLE III
PARAMETER ESTIMATED FOR ADDITIVE AND INTERACTION SPATIO-TEMPORAL MODEL WITH LATITUDE AS A COVARIATE

Parameter	Coefficient	Standard Deviation	Quantile 0.025	Quantile 0.5	Quantile 0.975	Mode
Intercept	526.553	12.151	505.425	525.522	558.096	525.004
Latitude	-34.683	9.124	-55.378	-34.485	-16.688	-34.625
τ_{GEV}	0.000035	0.000023	0.000029	0.000035	0.000041	0.000035
ξ_{GEV}	0.077	0.0065	0.063	0.071	0.092	0.076
σ^2_v (spatially structured)	1.4×10^{-3}	0.001071	0.024618	0.002353	0.00031	0.009324
σ^2_v (spatially unstructured)	1.1×10^{-4}	0.000949	0.000156	0.000115	8.6×10^{-5}	0.000113
σ^2_γ (temporally structured)	5.13×10^{-5}	5.14×10^{-5}	0.000787	7.29×10^{-5}	1.4×10^{-5}	0.000292
σ^2_ϕ (temporally unstructured)	5.77×10^{-5}	5.09×10^{-5}	0.000848	8.79×10^{-5}	1.4×10^{-5}	0.000312
σ^2_δ (spatio-temporal interaction)	4.89×10^{-5}	5.03×10^{-5}	0.000893	6.9×10^{-5}	1.3×10^{-5}	0.000352

Table 4 presents parameters estimated in the additive model and the interactions with the monthly rainfall average and the longitude coordinates as explanatory variables. This model gives the smallest RMSEP and AAPE values. The estimated value which gives the positive monthly rainfall coefficient indicates that the greater the monthly rainfall make the greater the probability for extreme rainfall occurs. As for the positive longitude coefficient estimator, it indicates that increasingly eastward for the West Java region, the higher extreme rainfall may occur.

The proportion of spatial variance of the model describes as $frac_{spatial} = \frac{s_v^2}{s_v^2 + \sigma_\gamma^2}$, with $s_v^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - \bar{v})^2}{n-1}$. The proportion of spatial variance for models with latitude as explanatory variables is 0.929, while the proportion of spatial variance for models with longitude and average monthly rainfall as explanatory variables is 0.906, this means that models with latitude as covariates are better at explaining spatial diversity. While the proportion of temporal diversity calculates as $frac_{temporal} = \frac{s_\gamma^2}{s_\gamma^2 + \sigma_\phi^2}$, with $s_\gamma^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i - \bar{\gamma})^2}{n-1}$.

TABLE IV
PARAMETER ESTIMATED FOR ADDITIVE AND INTERACTION SPATIO-TEMPORAL MODEL WITH LONGITUDE AND THE AVERAGE MONTHLY RAINFALL AS A COVARIATE

Parameter	Coefficient	Standard Deviation	Quantile 0.025	Quantile 0.5	Quantile 0.975	Mode
Intercept	173.3579	181.8026	-193.4973	201.9745	465.0199	273.9369
Average Rainfall	2.1575	0.8411	0.9774	2.1085	3.9015	1.2870
Longitude	21.5408	73.7140	-109.1296	37.5230	127.4614	98.0056
τ_{GEV}	1.34×10^{-5}	1.58×10^{-7}	1.31×10^{-5}	1.34×10^{-5}	1.36×10^{-5}	1.35×10^{-5}
ξ_{GEV}	-0.20	0.0018	-0.203	-0.199	-0.196	-0.199
τ_v (spatially structured)	0.001289	0.0158	0.001518	0.001293	0.001103	0.001301
τ_v (spatially unstructured)	6.11×10^{-5}	0.000211	9.14×10^{-5}	6.62×10^{-5}	3.48×10^{-5}	8.16×10^{-5}
τ_γ (temporally structured)	2.89×10^{-5}	5.42×10^{-5}	3.1×10^{-5}	2.92×10^{-5}	2.56×10^{-5}	3.05×10^{-5}
τ_ϕ (temporally unstructured)	8.34×10^{-5}	0.000711	0.000105	8.43×10^{-5}	6.63×10^{-5}	8.63×10^{-5}
τ_δ (spatio-temporal interaction)	0.000106	0.001022	0.000136	0.000106	9×10^{-5}	0.000102

The proportion of temporal variability of the model with a latitude explanatory variable is 0.357, while a model with the longitude and the average monthly rainfall as explanatory variables gives a better proportion of temporal diversity, which is 0.470. Figure 5 shows the spatial influence of additive models and interactions with latitude as covariates. It shows that in zones 7, 8, and 9 around Jakarta, Depok, Bekasi areas and to the south of the Bogor region (zone 1) exert a strong spatial influence. Whereas in Ciamis (zone 19) and Kuningan (zone 4), which also have a strong spatial influence compared to other regions.

Fig. 5 The spatial effect of additive and interactions Spatio-temporal model with latitude as a covariate

Figure 6 illustrates the posterior mean of the spatial influence of additive and interaction models, using longitude and monthly average rainfall as explanatory variables. In Figure 6, it can be seen that zone 1 (Bogor region) has a strong spatial influence, as do zones 2, 15, 16, and 17, namely Purwakarta, Subang, Indramayu, and their surrounding areas, which also have a significant spatial influence.

Fig. 6 The spatial effect of additive and interactions Spatio-temporal models with covariates for longitude and monthly average rainfall

Figure 7 shows the map of the estimated extreme rainfall using additive models with latitude as a covariate. The estimated value of extreme rainfall exhibits a uniform pattern.

Fig. 7 Map of estimating extreme rainfall with the additive, interaction model of the latitude as the explanatory variable

The estimation of extreme rainfall from 1981 to 2012 reveals the highest value in the Southwest Java region. This indicates that the highest chance of extreme rainfall is in the Southwest Java region. The presumption pattern in Figure 7 also shows that the more towards the South, the greater the chance of extreme rainfall. This is in line with the estimation

of the parameters for the latitude coefficient, which results in a negative value, which also means that the more towards the South, the extreme the model estimation value is. When compared to the La Nina years as in 2001, 2007 and 2010, this model does not show a significant pattern of extreme rainfall increases. This finding is reinforced by the study of Sofiati et al. [42], who evaluated the performance of the WRF model for seasonal rainfall prediction in the Indonesian region. They showed that spatial configuration and geographical position greatly influenced the prediction accuracy, with regions such as central East Kalimantan and southern West Java showing significantly different rainfall intensity and bias potential compared to other regions.

Figure 8 shows a map of estimating extreme rainfall through additive models and interactions with the explanatory variables for longitude and monthly average rainfall.

Fig. 8 Map of estimating extreme rainfall with additive, interaction models with explanatory variables of longitude and monthly average rainfall

The estimated value in Figure 8 exhibits a varied pattern, both in terms of location and the time factor. In general, high values for all zones were found in the period 1984, 1985, 1986, 1992, 1995, 1996, 1998, 2001, 2007, and 2010. The zones that produce estimates for extremely high rainfall for each year are zones 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6. When compared to Figure 4, the extreme rainfall estimation map in Figure 8 results are closer to being better. When related to the La Nina years, such as 1984, 1985, 2001, and 2010, this model produces a corresponding estimate; this is evident from the high estimation in those years, even in 2001 and 2010. It shows the estimated value for extreme rainfall, which is the highest. However, this study contrasts with the research of Loua et al. [43], who analyzed rainfall and temperature variability in Conakry (Guinea) from 1960 to 2016 using statistical approaches such as the Mann-Kendall and Wavelet Analysis, and evaluated the relationship with global climate indices. The study identified long-term trends and their linkages with phenomena such as El Niño and Atlantic Niño. However, it has not integrated Bayesian-based spatial-

temporal structures nor extreme distributions (GEV) to detect the intensity of extreme rainfall events spatially.

The results of this study show that regions such as Bogor and Jakarta have a significant spatial influence on extreme rainfall patterns, especially during the La Nina phenomenon. This finding provides guidance for policy makers to prioritize these areas in disaster mitigation planning such as strengthening drainage infrastructure. In contrast to this research, research conducted by Liou et. al. [44], urban heat island (UHI) is a phenomenon that increases temperatures in urban areas, which can exacerbate the impact of heatwaves and cause health risks, such as heat stress and death from extreme temperatures .

The spatio-temporal model with additive and interaction components showed the best performance based on DIC (8196) and RMSEP (200.52) values. Latitude and monthly average rainfall variables are the most influential factors on extreme rainfall patterns in West Java. The negative latitude coefficient indicates that the further south, the higher the chance of extreme rainfall, consistent with the distribution pattern identified in the southern region of West Java. In contrast to other studies, research by Bojago et. al. [45] which highlighted the seasonal variations as well as the intensity of extreme rainfall in relation to the decreasing number of rainy days and topographic patterns, the dynamics of extreme rainfall, both in spatial and temporal aspects, which can support climate adaptation planning to reduce the risks associated with extreme weather phenomena in both regions .

Theoretically, this research contributes to the development of spatio-temporal modeling methods by integrating the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution and the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) method. This approach proved to be efficient in handling extreme data and provided a solid foundation for similar future research. The additive spatio-temporal model with interactions used in this study offers higher prediction accuracy compared to the grid-based or exponential distribution-based approaches widely used previously.

Practically, the results of this study have the potential to support disaster risk mitigation in the West Java region. Information on extreme rainfall-prone areas, such as Bogor and Jakarta, can be utilized to improve risk mitigation planning, including strengthening drainage infrastructure in vulnerable zones. In addition, the resulting extreme rainfall predictions can assist the agricultural sector in designing planting and harvesting schedules that are more adaptive to climate change. The findings are also relevant for planning infrastructure development that is more resilient to flooding and changes in extreme weather patterns.

Furthermore, this research opens up opportunities for validation and generalization of the model in other geographical areas. The developed model can be integrated with Internet of Things (IoT)-based technologies to produce faster and more responsive real-time predictions. Thus, this research not only strengthens the scientific base in the field of spatio-temporal modeling but also makes a real contribution in supporting climate resilience and disaster risk management.

IV. CONCLUSION

The best spatio-temporal extremes model is the additive model with interaction, where the main variable is latitude,

with a DIC value of 8196. The best prediction performance was shown by the model with longitude and mean annual rainfall variables, with an RMSEP value of 200.52. The model with latitude explained 92.9% of the spatial variability, while the model with longitude and rainfall explained 90.6%, emphasizing the importance of geographic and climatic factors in understanding extreme rainfall patterns.

Further research is recommended to validate the model in different regions with different geographical characteristics to ensure its generalizability and reliability. In addition, the integration of real-time data through Internet of Things (IoT)-based technologies can improve prediction accuracy and provide dynamic updates. Research can also explore other Bayesian methods or additional variables, such as land use and population density, to enrich the model. The creation of interactive predictive maps will greatly support the application of the results of this research in disaster mitigation and climate change adaptation planning, thus providing wider practical benefits.

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